

MODELING OF IN-PLANE VOID TRANSPORT DURING COMPOSITES PROCESSING

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1 Introduction and Motivation

The reduction of void content is critical for the production of high performance composite parts [1]. The presence of voids significantly reduces the mechanical properties of composites and increases design risk. High performance composites (i.e. aerospace parts) generally require < 1-2% void fraction for structural applications. A model experiment has been developed to explore in-plane void morphology and transport which may be encountered during prepreg processing. A clear acrylic flow cell is constructed in which a simulated resin and voids are injected to understand relative void velocity during resin flow and deformation. A flow visualization setup records resin and void movement. Of interest is how to maximize the relative velocity of the voids with respect to the resin flow front. This will provide approaches and understanding of how one can remove voids when they are very close to the resin flow front. The goal is to link the relative void dynamics to process parameters for manufacturing void free composite structures.

Fig 1. shows a schematic of a partially impregnated single layer prepreg during Out of Autoclave (OOA) processing. In this example, the resin and fiber are initially discrete phases. With the application of pressure and temperature, the resin begins to impregnate the fiber tow and fill the empty spaces around the fiber tows. Any bubbles or microvoids present in the resin will move with the resin into the fiber preform around the fiber tows. During OOA processing, the resin is typically driven by an applied vacuum pressure. The bubble or void can be extracted by the vacuum if it reaches the flow front during the resin impregnation step. If the microvoids are not able to reach the flow front they cannot be removed by the

applied vacuum and will be entrapped within the composite. Thus, an understanding of not only local resin flow, but coupled resin and void flow is very important for removal of voids during composites processing.

Fig. 1. A schematic of a partially impregnated during OOA processing. The goal is to model in-plane void migration during local fiber tow infusion.

2 Methodology

Prepreg processing requires understanding of how macroscopic process parameters, such as applied pressure and temperature, influence the microscale void mobility and migration. A model experimental setup was fabricated as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 to study the fundamental void migration dynamics in a moving viscous fluid to mimic important process physics that is encountered during in-plane OOA processing. The goal is to study the relative velocity of the bubbles with respect to the velocity of the fluid flow front. The model experiment in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 observes moving air bubbles in a simulated resin (i.e. glycerin, corn syrup, silicone oil, etc.). The bubble velocity and flow velocity in the flow cell are

recorded for different process parameters and bubble diameters.

The setup consists of two clear parallel acrylic plates separated by a metal spacer. Silicone gaskets are fitted in between the acrylic plates and the metal spacer for sealing. The flow cell thickness can be modified by introducing different sized spacers. Inlet and outlet holes are cut to inject resin and introduce voids. Vacuum is applied at the outlet to drive the flow. A scale measures the resin mass flow rate during injection. Air bubbles are introduced by the removal of the injection line from the resin bucket. The baseline experimental parameters are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 2. In-plane void migration model setup with assembly view (top) and top down view (bottom).

Glycerin was selected as it provides sufficient contrast to demarcate the bubble domain versus resin domain sufficiently for image processing. The viscosity of the resin is recorded before each experiment with a Brookfield DV-E viscometer. A PC connected camera and florescent lighting is positioned above the center of the flow cell to record

the bubble motion. The position, time, and size of bubbles are extracted from camera images using the *ImageJ* image processing software. This provides the bubble velocity and the bubble morphology with respect to the moving resin flow front.

Fig. 3. Photograph of in-plane void migration visualization setup with the following components: (1) Resin line, (2) Scale, (3) Lamp, (4) Clamp, (5) Camera, (6) Camera field of view, (7) Vacuum port.

The experimental work is divided into two setup configurations. The first configuration observes bubble migration in the gap which is fully saturated with resin. This is illustrated in Fig. 5. The bubble velocity is calculated from the position/time data obtained from image analysis. The resin velocity is obtained from the mass flow rate data of the resin bucket. The target was to introduce bubbles of the order of 1.0 cm diameter. Bubbles that are found too small in diameter are not in contact with both the top and bottom parallel plates. This would make those bubbles not applicable to the experimental modeling and are rejected from the analysis. Note there is sufficient contrast between the resin bubble interface and the interior / exterior of the bubble as shown in the photograph of Fig.5.

Table 1. Baseline experimental parameters.

Name	Value	Description
ΔP	0.900 atm	Applied vacuum pressure
μ	1.000 Pa*s	Resin viscosity
γ	0.640 N/m	Resin/air surface tension
L_{cell}	20.320 cm	Flow cell length
W_{cell}	7.620 cm	Flow cell width
h_{cell}	0.635 cm	Flow cell gap thickness

Fig. 5. Bubble in flow cell experimental configuration schematic (top) and photograph (bottom). Injected bubbles are introduced in a fully saturated flow cell.

The second configuration observes void migration as the resin is filling the cell. This is illustrated in Fig. 6. Here, the resin velocity is obtained from the mass flow rate data of the resin bucket as the resin is filling the cell. Bubbles are introduced such that the flow front of the resin into the empty mold and the introduced bubbles are within the same visual window. Bubble velocity is obtained with the same image capturing scheme as the first configuration. The goal is to observe if the bubble will move closer to the moving resin front rapidly and coalesce with the resin front.

This topic of resin film drainage between moving bubbles and free surfaces (or flow fronts) was explored in a computational study by Gangloff et al. (2012) in [5]. The role of surface tension facilitating bubble coalescence with a flow front becomes very significant, closer the bubble is to the flow front. Pigeonneau and Sellier (2011) in [11] studied the problem of a rising bubble in a column filled with a viscous fluid with a fixed free surface. They noted that with higher the surface tension, the bubble will

reach the free surface faster by draining the resin film in between the bubble and the free surface. Debregeas et al. (1998) in [12] experimentally observed the rapid exponential decay of the resin film between oncoming bubbles released in a silicone oil bath towards the free surface.

Fig. 6. Bubbles in flow front experimental configuration schematic (top) and photograph (bottom). Injected bubbles are introduced very close to the moving resin flow front.

3 A Simplified Model

Fig. 7 displays a schematic of a model that is used to formulate understanding of the moving bubble in between the acrylic parallel plates. A key assumption is that the bubble is in contact with both channel surfaces during its motion. A force balance on the bubble between the surface tension adhesion force and hydrodynamic drag force is used to derive the critical conditions for dislodging bubbles from the channel walls and initiating bubble motion.

A primary aim of this setup is to quantify the influence of bubble size and resin velocity on the bubble mobility. A parameter coined as the bubble mobility is defined as the ratio between the average velocity of a bubble (U) versus the average velocity of the resin flow (V) as shown in [2],

$$\text{Bubble Mobility} \equiv U/V. \quad (2)$$

This parameter can quantify the relative velocity of the bubble with respect to the resin. A key criterion for ensuring void migration will be to have the bubble mobility greater than unity (i.e. $U/V > 1$). This can increase the probability of voids to dislodge from the resin and enter vacuum pathways to be removed from the system before cure. A bubble mobility greater than unity implies the bubble is moving faster than the resin. Understanding the effect of process and material parameters on the bubble mobility will allow one to select parameters to increase bubble mobility in composites processing.

The simplified model predicts steady state bubble mobility. The initial acceleration the bubble has from the start of the flow is very complex as noted by Maxey and Riley (1982) in [6]. As resin flow is always at a very small Reynolds number (i.e. $Re \ll 1$), the inertial effects of the moving bubble can be ignored; however, the forcing on the bubble as noted in [6] still contains time dependent terms. For composites processing, the steady state bubble velocity is of practical interest. It can be shown that for very small Re flow, the acceleration of the bubble to constant velocity is very fast and the measured velocity can be considered steady state.

Fig. 7. An in-plane schematic of the simplified bubble model.

Relevant dimensionless parameters are the capillary number (Ca) and the dimensionless bubble size (D') as noted in [3] which are listed below,

$$Ca = \mu V / \gamma, \quad (3)$$

$$D' = D_c / h. \quad (4)$$

The capillary number is the ratio of viscous stresses ($\mu V / D_c$) to interfacial stresses (γ / D_c). Note μ is the resin dynamic viscosity and γ is the resin surface tension. The capillary number can also be thought of as a scaled resin velocity. The dimensionless bubble size is the ratio of the contact diameter (D_c) and the flow gap height (h). The effect of these parameters on bubble mobility is experimentally characterized.

A similar experimental configuration of viscous liquid/bubble flow in between parallel plates was presented by Rabaud et al. (2011) in [4]. A power law relationship between bubble mobility, dimensionless bubble size, and capillary number was presented as follows,

$$\frac{U}{V} \cong 24\pi \left(\frac{D_c}{2h}\right)^2 \frac{a_{fluid}}{a_{wall}} \left[\left(\frac{2h}{D_c}\right)^3 Ca\right]^{1-\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Rabaud et al. (2011) notes three empirical parameters to characterize the relative velocity of the bubble. Here, a_{fluid} characterizes deviation of the bubble from being purely cylindrical. In addition, a_{wall} and α characterizes the bubble-wall friction/lubrication interaction effects. This model will be compared to the experimental results generated with the experimental setup presented in Section 2.

In composites processing it is of practical interest to understand the relationship between the bubble mobility, dimensionless bubble size, and the capillary number. For example, given a range of bubble sizes (D_c) normalized by fiber preform length scale (h), one can relate the capillary number (Ca) to process variables as a function of bubble mobility (U/V) and chose a process window that ensures that the bubble mobility is greater than unity. Rohatgi et al. (1996) found that the overall void content in the cured composite can be related to an optimum processing capillary number in [7]. Thus one can correlate bubble mobility to successful evacuation of bubbles during flow.

4 Results and Discussion

Fig. 8 displays a time-lapse example result of bubble migration in the flow cell. Here the flow cell was fully saturated with resin before the introduction of the bubble. Note the camera is oriented such that the bubble is moving from the top to the bottom of the camera field of view. The smaller bubbles that are present in the figure were generated as the mass of air exited from the inlet port initially. They are not analyzed in this work as they do not touch the top and bottom parallel plates. The bubbles maintain a very circular shape throughout their residence time in the flow cell.

Fig. 8. Bubble movement in flow cell at $Ca = 0.2202$.

Fig. 9 displays a time-lapsed example result of bubble movement in the flow cell that is being saturated with resin so one can notice the movement of the resin flow front. It is timed such that the bubble is close to the flow front and they pass together in the camera field of view. Of particular interest is the distance between the bubble and the flow front. This distance can be tracked to observe how effective the bubble is at meeting the flow front based on processing conditions. The bubble velocity can be directly

compared to the flow front velocity from the image processing analysis.

Fig 9. Movement of the Bubbles with the flow front at $Ca = 0.0656$

Fig. 10 displays a time-lapsed example result of bubble movement in relation to the flow front. Here, multiple bubbles are introduced with the flow front into an empty flow cell. The bubbles meet the flow front, coalesce, and escape the flow. It is hypothesized that the resin film drainage near the flow front during bubble approach leads to accelerated coalescence and rupture. The bubble is thought to be driven to the flow front due to the surface tension effects as noted earlier. A key composites processing goal to reduce the distance between the flow front and bubble is via selection of optimized process parameters. This can be sought for RTM process scales (i.e. macro scale flow front) or OOA process scales (i.e. millimeter scale flow fronts).

Fig. 11 displays a chart that shows the combined experimental results for the bubble in saturated flow

cell and bubble in flow cell that is being filled in which the resin flow front is also tracked. In addition, the power law fits are plotted as lines. The scaling of the chart is based on the scaling presented by Rabaud et al (2011) in [4]. Here, the relationship between the bubble mobility, dimensionless bubble size, and process capillary number is quantified. Note that Table 2 shows the fitting parameters derived from the experimental results to match with the model proposed in [4]. These correspond to power law fitting parameters based on equation (5). In addition, each data point shown in Fig. 11 corresponds to one steady state bubble mobility value at a given dimensionless bubble size and process capillary number.

Table 2. Fitting parameters derived from experimental results as shown in Fig. 11.

Experimental configuration	a_{fluid} / a_{wall}	$1 - \alpha$	α
Bubbles in saturated flow cell	0.0194	0.4121	0.5879
Bubbles when the flow cell has a moving flow front	0.0512	0.3576	0.6424

Fig. 10. Bubbles approaching and coalescing with the flow front at $Ca = 0.0401$

Fig. 11. Experimental results plotted with model proposed by Rabaud et al. (2011) in [4]. The results show a power law relationship can be found between bubble mobility, size and processing driven capillary number.

The results shown in Fig. 11 show a significantly better bubble mobility for the case where bubbles are being convected with moving flow fronts versus their movement in a saturated cell subjected to steady flow. This suggests that voids can be dislodged when they are in the vicinity of a moving resin flow. This is usually present during processing of composites in which the resin is being displaced to cover the empty space between fibers.

It should be noted in Fig. 11 that as it was significantly more difficult to introduce bubbles with a moving resin flow front to pass together through the field of view, there is less data plotted for this configuration. Significant scatter present in Fig. 11 can be attributed to our bubble introduction scheme. Work is ongoing to better improve the experimental methodology and improve the experimental setup.

The determined ratios of a_{fluid}/a_{wall} suggest a strong dependence of the bubble migration on the resin film dynamics between the top and bottom plates versus the flow around the surface normal to the incoming resin flow around the bubble. Rabaud et al. (2011) notes how the phenomenological exponent α has been cited to fall between 1/2 and 2/3 based on thin film bubble lubrication theory [4]. We report our α values fall in between these limits.

The exponent is related to the power law scaling of the capillary number Ca^α and its relationship to the ratio of the resin thin film δ normalized by the flow cell thickness h such that $\delta/h \sim Ca^\alpha$. The theory in [4] notes that this exponent relates the lubrication of the bubble with the top and bottom flow cell parallel walls. The dimensionless α values determine the magnitude of the resin film thickness between the bubble and the walls. Based on this thickness, the bubble can exceed the average velocity of the flow around the bubble due to the “aquaplaning” effect or Bretherton lubrication [8]. Fig. 12 depicts this schematically in the context of composites processing. Note the term λ denotes the transition region where resin lubrication effects begin to take place. This lubrication causes a slip velocity on the bubble to better mobilize it in the resin flow. Thus, the Bretherton lubrication effects provide a physical basis for the bubble mobility to be greater than unity and why the power law scaling with capillary number and dimensionless bubble size are important.

Fig. 12. A schematic of resin and void flow through intratow channels during composites processing. The void in the intratow channels is modeled as a bubble through a duct after Bretherton (1961) in [8].

These results shed light on why voids during composites manufacturing can sometimes migrate faster than surrounding resin flow or are slower than the resin flow. This is observable during typical Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) of composites. The capillary number is shown to directly influence how well these lubrication films form around bubbles and walls. It can be imagined that a critical capillary number can be determined [7] such that the resin flow provides sufficient thin film thickness between the bubble and the walls or the fiber surfaces in order to provide sufficient lubrication and provide bubble mobility that is greater than unity.

In composites processing, the resin and voids travel through channels composed of porous media walls formed by fiber tow architectures. It is unclear what the effects of the porous media walls are on the resin and void velocities. As the resin and voids travel between fiber tows, the velocity around fiber tows is directly impacted by the resin flow into the fiber tows. The interaction of flow around fiber tows without bubbles has been analyzed analytically by Beavers and Joseph (1967) in [9] and Neale and Nader (1974) in [10] and numerically by Hwang and Advani (2010) in [13].

5 Summary and Conclusions

A model flow visualization experiment consisting of a flow channel between two acrylic parallel plates in which a simulated resin containing air bubbles was injected. Image processing was used to measure the relative bubble velocity with respect to the average resin velocity. The bubble mobility was quantified as a function of material and process parameters.

Results suggest that the bubbles experience the highest bubble mobility when the voids are nearest to resin flow fronts. This is believed to be related to the dominance of the surface tension at the flow front as the bubble approaches the flow front. The bubbles are shown to be able to migrate under optimized process conditions via the process capillary number for a given scaled bubble size. This is believed to be related to the lubrication dynamics of the thin resin film formed between the bubble and the top and the bottom walls. The thickness of this resin layer dictates the ability of the void to migrate faster than the resin flow as its thickness scales with the process capillary number and dimensionless bubble size. Thus, an ideal process capillary number can be found to capitalize on lubrication effects and expedite relative bubble motion to eliminate voids during composites processing.

In addition, a relationship between dimensionless bubble size, process capillary number, and bubble mobility can be found based on a simplified model proposed in the literature. These results should prove useful during processing of composite using OOA or RTM or VARTM processes in which one has a moving flow front. Future work will study the influence of porous media walls as the resin and voids flow to fill in the spaces between the fibers.

6 References

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